

FASTCAT-Cloud

Training & capacity building resources

Cos4Cloud Services

About the FASTCAT-Cloud system and user guide

This is a system and user guide to [FASTCAT-Cloud](#), An AI-based service that helps with species identification by automatically filtering out unwanted pictures from camera traps.

Description

FASTCAT-Cloud is a service that uploads and analyses nature videos and pictures filtering out the unwanted ones to the most relevant images and recordings of wildlife activity using Artificial Intelligence (AI) to identify species names.

FASTCAT-Cloud has been developed by [DynAlkon](#) As part of [Cos4Cloud](#), a European Horizon 2020 funded project. The Cos4Cloud project developed [thirteen services](#) boosting citizen science technological services to help increase and improve the quantity and quality of observations.

FASTCAT-Cloud is a web service which supports wildlife identification using AI. It can be used in two ways:

- i. the FASTCAT-Cloud App individual users can upload camera trap images or videos and have them analysed using the FASTCAT-Cloud App;
- ii. or the FASTCAT-Cloud API: developers, leaders of citizen observatories, other projects or initiatives can integrate the FASTCAT-Cloud API into their own platforms or systems where it can be integrated and made accessible.

Service Coordinator

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Cos4Cloud Coordinator

The following content has been provided to help guide users of this service.

WHAT IS FASTCAT-CLOUD?

FASTCAT (Flexible Ai System for CAmera Traps)-Cloud is a service that uploads and analyses nature videos and pictures filtering to relevant images and recordings of wildlife activity using Artificial Intelligence (AI) to identify species names.

FASTCAT is a web service which supports wildlife identification using AI. [FASTCAT-Cloud](#) is an API for this system, and it can be accessed using the [FASTCAT-Cloud App](#), a web interface that uses this API.

It allows users to upload camera trap images or videos of species observations to a server where they are automatically captured, filtered and analysed using specially trained models (i.e. deep neural networks). AI generated predictions are generated; wildlife is identified within the images or frames and downloadable results with ID confidence ratings are produced along with associated species names.

WHO IS THIS SERVICE FOR?

[DynAlkon](#) specialises in AI-based techniques to recognise and characterise shape, movement etc of living things and have made **FASTCAT-Cloud** available to developers, researchers and others who use camera traps to record wildlife activity with a need to improve the results from their recordings.

Camera traps can be triggered by the movement of plants/trees due to wind, not because an animal was present creating hundreds (or thousands) of unwanted pictures which users have to filter through. It can be used in two ways the [FASTCAT-Cloud App](#) or the [FASTCAT-Cloud API](#).

Users can upload camera trap images or videos directly and have them analysed using the [FASTCAT-Cloud App](#). It is currently available for UK mammals, Spanish mammals, UK Birds, UK pollinators and UK and European butterflies.

It is also a service aimed at supporting existing and new citizen science initiatives, i.e. citizen observatories focused on biodiversity, with an interest in using AI-based functionality to support wildlife identification for their users. Developers, leaders of projects or initiatives can integrate [FASTCAT-Cloud API](#) into their own platforms or systems where it can be integrated and made accessible. This interactive service

allows users to filter interesting images and or videos at a keystroke and upload them as observations.

Through the API, batches of observations are submitted including a video or a set of images, with location, time, as well as optional environmental sensor data. The API provides results of Deep Neural Network annotations (including a bounding box, species ID and confidence rating). Data can then be either deleted or uploaded to **FASTCAT-Cloud**; store a subset of interesting observations on the **FASTCAT-Cloud** server for later use; or submit these as observations to a citizen observatory such as *iSpot*, see [Using the FASTCAT-Cloud App on iSpot](#) below. For further information about how *iSpot* and others have used FASTCAT-Cloud see the *Case Studies* and *Best Practice Guidelines* sections of the [Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub](#).

FASTCAT-Cloud currently filters a limited range of species but tailor-made models can be created to meet exact needs. For more information contact: info@dynaikon.com.

Planned features include:

- Allowing users to create accounts so we that we can increase the amount of observations that you can upload in each request
- Supporting processing of video observations
- Filtering out any images containing humans and any empty images
- Allowing users to specify which species they are interested in and only return images containing these species

WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS OF THIS SERVICE?

FASTCAT-Cloud provides a mechanism to view, store and identify species observations from camera trap images and videos. Specifically, it also:

- Saves time in selecting images and videos from camera traps: the website server greatly reduces the amount of unwanted data by automatically filtering out most unwanted pictures and video streams, keeping images of animals.
- More easily identifies species names through the integration of machine learning technology. By automatically identifying species, it allows one to see suggested species names for each image. The system is currently trained using species data from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF).
- Provides a way to automatically generate statistics, e.g. the number of species recorded or photographed, i.e. how many different species have been sighted this week, or how many times you have photographed a fox in the last 30 days.

- Has the potential to shares wildlife images with citizen observatories, citizen science projects, or platforms. For example, if you are a citizen scientist, recorder or nature enthusiast that uses a camera trap, you would be able to easily upload pictures to **iSpot** and view the proposed species name by uploading the observation.

HOW DOES IT WORK?

FASTCAT-Cloud is a web service that allows users to interactively upload camera trap images or videos to a server. It integrates an AI model that decide which frames, both images and videos, contain an animal. It automatically analyses and identifies species removing images that are not useful (e.g. no animals present, near duplicates, false positives due to wind movement, etc.) and allows the user to automatically update the number of species, both from videos and pictures.

This service performs by providing automatic analysis of data and make the entire processing of images much easier. This mainly involves three steps:

- i. Filtering: to remove most frames that are not useful
- ii. Providing bounding boxes around animals in images as well as counting species recording
- iii. Implementing automatic species identification in each bounding box

HOW TO USE FASTCAT-CLOUD – A STEP BY STEP GUIDE

TRY THE FASTCAT-CLOUD APP :

01

To use the service go to: <https://service.fastcat-cloud.org/app>

02

Select and the images of mammals, birds or butterflies you would like to use.

03

Select the 'model' you would like to use. The options currently available are:

- UK mammals (regular and faster running – includes 40 classes of mammals)
- Spanish mammals (includes 60 classes of mammals)
- UK birds (includes 268 classes of birds)
- UK butterflies (includes 62 classes of butterflies)
- European butterflies (includes 212 classes of butterflies)
- UK Pollinators (includes 221 classes of pollinators)
- Other (Cascade option)

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Have the images or videos you would like to upload available and ready for submission: up to 10 can be uploaded at a time.

We are constantly developing new models to detect more species. If there are particular species that you would like to detect that aren't included then please get in touch and we would be excited to arrange expediting creating a model for your particular needs.

Upload images/videos - maximum of 10 files
Select images/videos

Choose files No file chosen

submit

Select model

- Faster RCNN - UK Mammals
- Faster RCNN - UK Mammals
- YOLOR - UK Mammals
- YOLOR - Spain Mammals
- YOLOR - UK Birds
- YOLOR - UK Butterflies
- YOLOR - Europe Butterflies
- YOLOR - UK Pollinators
- Cascade R-CNN X-101 (v2) - CCT

DynAlkon Privacy Policy Contact

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To conduct a search 'choose files' to be uploaded. Select 'model', choose from the species groups available, and click 'submit':

Upload images/videos - maximum of 10 files
Select images/videos

Choose files large_N2_7317.jpg MDodd - owl for FC test.jpg

submit

Select model

YOLOR - UK Birds

06

If available, this will show in the 'Detection Summary'. Results will then be filtered and the predictions made available for download:

The screenshot shows three panels in the FASTCAT interface:

- Detection Summary:** A list of species with radio buttons. 'Empty' is selected with a count of 'x0', and 'Short-Eared Owl' is selected with a count of 'x1'.
- Filter Results:** A section with instructions: "Check the box next to a species name to display images containing the selected species. Use the download button at the bottom to download the selected results." Below this, there are two checked checkboxes for 'Empty' and 'Short-Eared Owl'. At the bottom are 'Download JSON' and 'Toggle All' buttons.
- Download Predictions:** A section with the text "Download all of the images in .json format." and a 'Download JSON' button.

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The confidence level of the prediction will be demonstrated as a percentage:

The screenshot shows a detection result for a 'Short-Eared Owl' with a '67% Confidence' level. The 'Detection Location' is listed as '354, 242, 436, 272'. To the left is a photograph of a field with a red bounding box around a bird in the distance.

Image: Short-eared owl *Asio flammeus* ©Mike Dodd

USING THE FASTCAT-CLOUD APP IN iSPOT:

iSpot (www.iSpotnature.org) has integrated FASTCAT-Cloud as an image recognition technology available to users. On iSpot FASTCAT-Cloud makes suggestions for some species groups when an observation is added from within the species groups available, applying automated image recognition to the main image posted in an observation of some UK mammal and bird species. More groups are being integrated as they become available.

The screenshot shows a comment section on iSpot titled 'Comments'. A comment from 'FASTCATcloud' is displayed, titled 'Automated suggestions from FASTCAT-cloud'. The comment text reads: "iSpot is trialling image recognition technologies from our Cos4Cloud partners to make suggestions for some species groups. Applying automated image recognition to the primary image, FASTCAT made the following suggestions: Rock Dove *Columba livia*". Below the text is a small image of a Rock Dove. At the bottom of the comment, there is a 'Reply' button and a 'Report content as inappropriate' button.

For more information and tips on using **FASTCAT-Cloud** as a service on iSpot see: [iSpot and AI](#)

USING THE FASTCAT-CLOUD API :

For information about integrating the API, go to: <https://service.fastcat-cloud.org/api>

The full API spec can be seen and downloaded on the specification page: <https://service.fastcat-cloud.org/api/spec>

INFORMATION AND FURTHER SUPPORT

Introduction to this Cos4Cloud service: <https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/services/fastcat-cloud-camera-trap/>

Try the FAST-CAT Cloud App: <https://service.fastcat-cloud.org/app>

Go to FASTCAT-Cloud here: <https://service.fastcat-cloud.org/>

Help with using this service can be found here: <https://service.fastcat-cloud.org/api#getting-started>

API documentation can be found here: <https://service.fastcat-cloud.org/api/spec>

FAQs: <https://service.fastcat-cloud.org/api#getting-started>

Contact: info@dynaikon.com

Access this service from the EOSC Marketplace: FASTCAT-Cloud: Flexible AI System for CAmera Trap images on the cloud

Get the Cos4Cloud infographic for this service: FASTCAT-Cloud Infographic

Additional resources: About the Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub

This system and user guide is a training resource for FASTCAT-Cloud, one of the technological services co-designed by the Cos4Cloud project (<https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/>). **Title: FASTCAT-Cloud System and User Guide.** Service Coordinator: Dynaikon. This guide is one of the Training and Capacity Building resources in the Cos4Cloud Toolbox & Evidence Hub developed by the Open University in collaboration with project partners. Contact: cos4cloud-toolbox@open.ac.uk.

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